

ISic0394

I.Sicily inscription 0394

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Paris, France, Museum Desnoyers

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR141201

1. Avitianus fide
2. lis hic in pace Chr (ist) i
3. quiescit qui vixit
4. an (nis) X[II] requievit
5. d (ie) XVI K (a) I (endas) April (es)
6. cons (ulum) Theodosi XV
7. et Fl (avi) Valentiniani II.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491605

EDR 141201

EDCS 21900435

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7113 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Le Blant, Edmond Frédéric 1856. Inscriptions chrétiennes de la Gaule antérieures au VIIIe siècle. Paris. At xxxvii

Diehl, Ernst Johann L. 1925. Inscriptiones Latinae Christianae Veteres. Berlin. At 1357

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